

On capturing effects of medication change in Parkinson’s disease with wrist accelerometry-based digital biomarkers

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Abstract—Parkinson’s disease (PD) motor symptoms are characterized by fluctuations, rendering their monitoring and therapy personalization challenging. Wrist-worn accelerometers serve as objective digital biomarkers (dBMs) for continuous monitoring of PD symptoms. The aim of this study is to investigate if dBMs of upper limb mobility, passively captured via a single wrist-worn accelerometer, can be indicative of motor function improvement due to increase in Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (LEDD) in People with Parkinson’s (PwP). Daily accelerometer data of PwP from the Verily Study Watch cohort of the Parkinson’s Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) study were filtered to isolate clinically relevant non-tremor gross movements and then processed to estimate digital biomarkers of mobility in periods before and after LEDD change. Repeated measures correlation analysis revealed significant ($p < 0.05$) positive correlations of range of motion ($r = 0.32$), peak acceleration ($r = 0.26$) and jerk ($r = 0.38$) with LEDD increase. Preliminary longitudinal and intraday analyses further point to the dBMs’ utility in tracking medication effects, revealing distinct changes in motor activity and symptom dynamics before and after medication adjustments. These findings suggest that wrist-based accelerometry features offer meaningful, continuous measures for remote monitoring and personalized PD management, potentially informing proactive treatment modifications and enhancing patient quality of life.

Parkinson’s disease, digital biomarkers, wearable sensors, accelerometry, medication management, LEDD, motor fluctuations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson’s disease (PD) is characterized by fluctuating motor symptoms, rendering symptom monitoring and management challenging. Clinicians often adjust dopaminergic therapy via a “trial and error” process based on infrequent in-clinic patient snapshots that sometimes lead to suboptimal regimens and unnecessary burden.

Continuous monitoring with wearable devices, such as wrist-worn accelerometers, offer objective, high-resolution insights into specific motor symptoms [1]. Wearable devices are highly suitable for unobtrusive, long-term remote monitoring due to their scalability, cost-effectiveness, and patient compliance [2]. This aligns with growing evidence on the utility of wearable devices in detecting medication-related

motor changes [3]. Although there is growing evidence supporting the utility of wearables to identify gait symptoms, their value for capturing subtle motor symptoms, such as tremors, slowness of movement, and medication-induced dyskinesias, remains a challenge.

Previous studies using wrist-worn wearables showed that accelerometer-derived statistical features, specifically the root-mean-square (RMS) acceleration magnitude and the signal magnitude area (SMA), correlated with clinician-rated dyskinesia severity during activities of daily living [4], [5]. While multi-sensor systems, combining inertial sensors on various body parts (e.g., wrists, ankles, trunk), have demonstrated improved detection of tremor, bradykinesia, dyskinesia, and gait disturbance [6], each additional device increases cost and wearer burden. Single-sensor solutions offer compelling advantages; for instance, a single waist-worn sensor has been shown to estimate dyskinesia severity with good concurrent validity [7]. Wrist-only solutions deliver continuous and objective motor metrics and achieve greater long-term adherence because they are unobtrusive and easy to maintain [8]–[10]. These advances are promising and support personalized and real-world PD management.

We previously introduced a wrist-based digital biomarker (dBM) to quantify slowness of movement of People with Parkinson’s (PwP) in daily life [11]. Building on that work, we now test whether the same wrist-derived, non-gait kinematic features are responsive to changes in dopaminergic medication. Our aim is to explore whether increases in Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (LEDD) are translated to measurable changes in wrist-based dBMs of mobility. For each participant we assess these kinematic features in two time windows, six weeks before and six weeks after each documented LEDD increase, and we also examine their diurnal profiles. We hypothesize that the filtered wrist signals will show significant within-subject shifts following LEDD increases, capturing therapy-related changes in upper-limb motor dynamics.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

A. Dataset and Preprocessing

To perform the analysis, we used wrist accelerometer data from the Verily Study Watch dataset available through the Parkinson’s Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) [12]. Participants were included if they had at least two consecutive study visits with a documented medication change and contributed a minimum of seven valid wear days (≥ 12 h between 06:00–22:00) in both the pre- and post-adjustment windows.

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Fig. 1. Longitudinal median peak-acceleration trend for one patient surrounding a +100 mg LEDD adjustment. The plot, showing daily medians and linear fits, suggests a potential shift from a declining to an increasing trend in movement vigor following the medication increase.

TABLE I

SAMPLE DEMOGRAPHICS AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS; PWP: PEOPLE WITH PARKINSON’S; AVG.: AVERAGE; STD: STANDARD DEVIATION; MDS-UPDRS: MOVEMENT DISORDERS SOCIETY UNIFIED PARKINSON’S DISEASE RATING SCALE; H&Y: HOEHN & YAHR STAGE; LEDD: LEVODOPA EQUIVALENT DAILY DOSE.

No. of PwP	34
Demographics	
Females	12
Males	22
Avg. Age (std)	68.06 (8.54)
Clinical characteristics	
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	6.68 (2.06)
Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III (Motor Examination) total score (std)	27.77 (12.29)
Avg. H&Y Stage (std)	1.92 (0.45)
Avg. LEDD in mg (std)	663.52 (372.74)

Participants were excluded if they lacked two qualifying visits, or had missing demographic/clinical data required for LEDD calculation. Participants who had already received deep brain stimulation (DBS) were also excluded because chronic high-frequency stimulation of the subthalamic nucleus or the pallidum globus can improve bradykinesia, tremor and dyskinesia, and typically allows a 30–50% reduction in dopaminergic medication, thus obscuring motor fluctuations attributable solely to pharmacological dose changes [13]. After applying these criteria, the final sample size was $n = 34$ PwP, whose clinico-demographic information is summarized in Table I.

Raw 3-axis acceleration signals (initially sampled at 100 Hz) were segmented into non-overlapping 5-s windows and then downsampled to 25 Hz, a typical sampling frequency of commercial wrist wearables. Subsequently, building on our previous methodology [11], our pipeline detected hand movement while excluding gait periods, focusing on clinically relevant upper extremity movements. All remaining acceleration signals were pre-processed in two steps. First, a 6th-order low-pass Butterworth filter with a cut-off fre-

quency of 3 Hz was applied to the signal vector magnitude during hand movement detection to isolate gross upper limb movement and isolate high-frequency noise. Second, a fourth-order Butterworth band-pass filter ([0.25 – 3.00] Hz) was then applied to each 5-s segment, suppressing tremor frequencies while preserving the spectral content of non-tremorous movements. The valid segments were then pooled into 10-minute intervals.

B. Feature Extraction

We extracted a set of features from the signal vector magnitude of each 10-minute interval of preprocessed accelerometer data. These features and their clinical interpretations are detailed in Table II, with detailed calculations available in [11].

TABLE II
FEATURES EXTRACTED FROM EACH 10-MIN INTERVAL OF
PREPROCESSED ACCELEROMETER DATA

Feature Name	Clinical Interpretation
Peak acceleration	Movement vigor, inversely associated with slowness of movement
Range of motion	Limb displacement, reflecting slowness of movement
Jerk	Movement smoothness, sensitive to involuntary movements
Signal entropy	Complexity of acceleration pattern, tracks changes in movement

C. Medication Modification Analysis

In the PPMI dataset, medication change dates are truncated to a month-level for privacy reasons; thus, day-level dates of medication changes are not available. To address the resulting limited temporal resolution, we excluded from the analysis the entire reported month of medication adjustment as a buffer period. We then analyzed two fixed 45-day windows, one immediately *before* and one immediately *after* this buffer period (Fig. 1). This approach ensured that the observed signal changes were more likely to reflect sustained effects

Fig. 2. Repeated measures correlations between Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (LEDD) and four wrist-based digital biomarkers across all 34 participants. Each panel illustrates the intra-subject longitudinal correlation for (a) Range of Motion Magnitude median, (b) Peak Acceleration Magnitude median, (c) Signal Entropy Magnitude median, and (d) Jerk Magnitude median. The repeated measures correlation analysis fits separate parallel regression lines for each participant, all sharing a common slope but having varying intercepts, reflecting the common within-individual association between medication scheme and mobility characteristics while accounting for individual differences in baseline levels.

of the adjustment, rather than transitional or ambiguous timing around the change itself. We restricted the analysis to medication modifications in which the LEDD increased relative to the previous medication plan. Within each 45-day window, features derived from 10-min epochs were first averaged per day. A day was considered valid when at least 12 h of wear time were present between 06:00 and 22:00, and a window was retained only if it contained a minimum of seven valid days. The daily values were then summarized by their median to yield one representative feature per participant per window. To assess symptom dynamics *before* and *after* dose adjustment via visual comparison, we obtained intraday profiles by generating paired diurnal curves for visual comparison of symptom dynamics around the medication change. These curves were created by averaging the 10-minute features into successive 2-hour bins, calculated independently for pre- and post-medication adjustment periods.

III. RESULTS

Using repeated measures correlation [14], we found that LEDD was positively associated with three wrist-derived

digital biomarkers (Fig. 2). Median peak-acceleration magnitude increased with LEDD ($r = 0.26$, $p = 0.035$), as did median range-of-motion magnitude ($r = 0.32$, $p = 0.009$) and median jerk magnitude ($r = 0.38$, $p = 0.001$). These findings indicate that higher dopaminergic doses generally correspond to greater movement amplitude and abruptness. In contrast, median signal entropy magnitude exhibited a weak, non-significant negative relationship with LEDD ($r = -0.15$, $p = 0.24$). This lack of a significant correlation for signal entropy may be attributed to the inherent noise characteristics of accelerometer signals, which can obscure the subtle, non-linear patterns that entropy aims to quantify.

Temporal patterns in the digital biomarkers were explored visually, providing qualitative insights into medication effects. Figure 1 illustrates a representative longitudinal trend of median peak acceleration in the period surrounding a positive LEDD adjustment. As shown, the linear trend of median peak acceleration typically exhibited a slight decline before the medication change, followed by a notable shift to a modest rise after the adjustment. This visual observation suggests a transition from reduced to increased movement vigor following LEDD modification.

Fig. 3. Indicative intraday median peak acceleration profiles for two PwP, suggesting person-specific improvement in movement vigor observed after medication adjustment.

As an exploratory step for within-day patterns, the intraday profile of median peak acceleration was also analyzed. Figure 3 illustrates these profiles for two representative Parkinson’s patients, highlighting distinct responses to medication adjustment. Patient A (top panel) demonstrates a notable increase in peak acceleration following medication change, particularly pronounced in the morning hours (between 08:00 and 10:00) and also showing an upward trend in the early afternoon to evening (between 14:00 and 18:00). Patient B (bottom panel) exhibits an increase in peak acceleration primarily in the morning (between 08:00 and 10:00 h) following the medication adjustment. The exact daily schedule of participants was not available, precluding more detailed intraday analysis at this stage.

IV. DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to determine whether intra-subject changes in LEDD are reflected in corresponding changes in wrist accelerometer-derived features. After suppressing the tremor frequency band, higher LEDD consistently produced larger and more forceful upper limb movements, while complexity (measured in terms of signal entropy) did not change. Clinically, bradykinesia and rigidity are the most levodopa-responsive motor features, showing rapid gains in movement amplitude and speed soon after dosing, whereas dyskinesias typically emerge only after prolonged or higher-dose exposure [1], [15]. The modest rise in jerk could indicate a quantifiable trade-off between improved motor vigor and emerging involuntary bursts—potentially relevant for fine-tuning therapeutic adjustments.

The temporal patterns observed in these digital biomarkers can offer valuable insights into medication effects, suggesting their potential clinical utility. For example, the shift in the six-week trajectory of median peak acceleration (Fig. 1) from a declining to an upward slope, following a 100 mg LEDD

increase, suggests a progressive improvement in bradykinesia consistent with what clinicians would expect to verify at the next follow-up visit. Likewise, the intraday curves for two representative patients in Fig.3 can reveal an immediate rise in morning peak acceleration (around 08:00–10:00), typically when many patients experience early-morning akinesia [16]. Detecting that boost remotely could reassure clinicians that the new regimen is taking effect, or, if absent, the clinician could modify the regimen, establishing a faster, data-driven titration loop with the patient rather than waiting weeks for an in-person visit. These temporal observations are consistent with a medication-related improvement in motor symptoms.

The current analysis carries certain limitations. We did not stratify by age or activity type, both of which can influence accelerometry metrics [17]. Our current analysis intentionally filtered out tremorous movements to isolate non-tremorous symptoms, despite tremor being a frequent and often medication-responsive symptom in PwP. While this allowed for a focused analysis of slowness of movement and dyskinesia within the (0.25–3.00) Hz band, a more holistic view of the medication-responsiveness cycle would be a key focus of future work, and would require the explicit incorporation and differentiation of tremor, bradykinesia, and dyskinesia. This would require further validation and potentially integration of additional clinical labels. Future investigation into signal entropy involves its analysis after decomposition into separate oscillatory modes. This approach could potentially mitigate noise masking and offer a more nuanced understanding of movement complexity. A significant limitation is the month-level precision of LEDD adjustment records. Furthermore, the inherent day-to-day variability in free-living accelerometry data, particularly in a fluctuating condition like PD, can complicate the precise quantification of subtle medication-induced motor changes over time. Future work should integrate high-resolution medication adherence data for more accurate temporal alignment. We also did not explicitly model postural instability, which might be revealed by trunk accelerometry [18]. The relatively modest sample size imposed a constraint on our ability to conduct robust subgroup analyses (e.g., early vs. advanced disease, tremor-dominant vs. akinetic-rigid phenotypes). Moreover, the analysis did not account for potential influences from other non-dopaminergic medications or comorbidities, nor did it differentiate between various types of LEDD increases (e.g., dosage adjustments vs. introduction of new dopaminergic agents). Finally, we analyzed only LEDD increases. The responsiveness of these biomarkers to dose reductions, infusion therapies, or non-dopaminergic treatments should be further investigated.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we demonstrated that wrist-based accelerometry-derived digital biomarkers (dBMs) can detect subtle, levodopa-induced motor changes in individuals with Parkinson’s disease (PwP), even with dosage adjustments as small as 100 mg LEDD. These biomarkers showed consistent, albeit modest, correlations

($r \approx 0.3$) with LEDD across free-living conditions, aligning with prior sensor-based studies and confirming their clinical relevance. Crucially, the data were collected using wearable hardware that PwP generally tolerate well over long periods, reinforcing the real-world feasibility of these tools for longitudinal monitoring. The robustness of the signal—after filtering out tremors and excluding patients with deep brain stimulation—emphasizes the specificity of wrist-based dBM for capturing medication-related motor dynamics. Their continuous and objective nature makes them promising candidates for embedding into remote health platforms and personalized care pathways, moving beyond traditional episodic assessments toward proactive symptom management. Future work will focus on identifying clinically meaningful thresholds of dBM change that warrant LEDD adjustment. This involves correlating dBM shifts with patient-reported outcomes and validated scales such as UPDRS or MDS-UPDRS, with the ultimate goal of defining the smallest reliably detectable LEDD modification that yields a measurable digital response. Embedding these dBM into adaptive treatment systems could enable individualized titration strategies, improve motor control stability, reduce treatment delays, and enhance overall quality of life for PwP—while potentially lowering healthcare costs by facilitating remote, data-driven decisions.

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